

Validation of Diagnostic Test for Students with Learning Difficulties in Mathematics at Elementary Level

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 29, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 30, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Validation, Diagnostic Test, Students, Learning Difficulties, Mathematics, Elementary Level</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6612726</p>	<p><i>The goal of this study was to validate elementary-level diagnostic test for children with learning difficulties in mathematics. In Pakistan, there has been limited research on the Validation of Diagnostic Tests for Students with Learning Difficulties in Mathematics. This descriptive research's population of study includes eighth-grade students from public schools. A sample of 580 eighth-grade students was recruited at random from public schools for the purposes of this research. The screening checklist contained 35 elements related to Math learning problems. The data was scored and entered into the SPSS computer software. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data. Cronbach's Alpha was used to measure the reliability of the screening checklist, and the Pearson correlation coefficient was utilized to establish the concurrent validity of the screening checklist. When the screening checklist was assessed, there was a significant difference between students who scored low and those who scored high.</i></p>

Introduction

A disability is any physical or mental condition (impairment) that makes it more difficult for a person to undertake specific tasks (activity limitation) and interact with their surroundings (participation restrictions). Students with learning difficulties may struggle to stay up in class or pay attention when it comes to reading, writing, and arithmetic. These people may also be disengaged or show signs of poor social and psychological well-being (Shakespeare, 2017).

A neurodevelopmental issue that affects how a student behaves and/or processes information may result in a learning problem in the classroom in certain situations. This issue might be caused by environmental or physical causes that hinder their ability to learn. Long absences from school, economic issues, undiagnosed visual or hearing impairments, and socioeconomic factors, for example, may all lead to low academic performance (Landrigan et al., 2012).

Educators must understand inclusive education policies and practices in order to guarantee that all children and young people with learning disabilities are included. They must also be aware of each student's strengths and needs, and they must adopt ways to aid students as part of a holistic approach to teaching, learning, and assistance across the school (Gong et al., 2020).

According to experts, the key reasons why mathematics is a difficult topic for students are a lack of effort on their behalf as well as a lack of prerequisites. It was also observed that students' hesitation to seek help from others, inattention in the classroom, and a lack of excitement all contributed to their difficulty in learning mathematics (Acharya, 2017).

In Pakistan there is very little research conducted at Validation of Diagnostic Test for Students with Learning Difficulties in Mathematics at Elementary Level in Punjab. This research is conducted to fulfil this gap. This research study will help the research to understand the validation of diagnostic test for Students with Learning Difficulties in Mathematics at elementary level. This research was conducted to Validate the Diagnostic Test for Students with Learning Difficulties in Mathematics at Elementary Level in Punjab.

Literature Review

If your child is having trouble with math, you may be wondering what is causing the problem. Here are a few ideas. Was it dyscalculia that created the difficulties, or was it something else? There is only one way to know for sure. It will be important to have your child assessed for dyscalculia (which is now recognised as a "specific learning disorder," with areas of math inadequacy emphasized) (Kucian et al., 2011).

A comprehensive evaluation may reveal the precise areas in which your child is struggling. Evaluators evaluate a child's ability to do basic arithmetic, retain math material, and solve problems in a short period of time. Each dyscalculia exam looks at a different set of skills. To assess (Landerl & colleagues, 2004), the following tests may be used:

- Skills in computation
- Fluency in mathematics
- Mental calculation
- Reasoning quantitatively

There are many different fields of mathematics, such as arithmetic, arithmetic problem-solving, geometry, algebraic reasoning, probability, statistics, and calculus, all of which need the activation of a variety of foundational abilities such as number sense and symbol decoding. Mathematics may be difficult for children who lack one or more of these abilities or who have difficulties organizing their efforts. Researchers from a wide range of disciplines, including mathematics education, developmental and cognition psychology, and neuroscience, have long been interested in better understanding the cognitive structure and mechanisms that control mental growth in various mathematical areas (Dean & Whiting, 2019).

Dyscalculia patients have trouble comprehending and digesting mathematical concepts. Mental arithmetic and counting difficulties are only two of the many symptoms that patients may experience. Visit this page to find out more about this arithmetic learning issue, including its most likely causes and remedies. Dyscalculia is a mathematical learning disability that hinders a person's ability to understand number-related ideas, do proper arithmetic calculations, and reason and solve problems. 1 Dyscalculia is also known as "number dyslexia" or "math dyslexia" in certain circles. Children with ADHD are more likely to have dyscalculia (ADHD or ADD) than the general population. More than half of ADHD children have a learning disability, such as dyslexia or dysgraphia (Acharya, 2017).

There is no other explanation for persons with dyscalculia's difficulties in all parts of mathematics, including education, intellectual disabilities, or other conditions. Without the assistance of a professional, mathematical concepts such as telling time, counting money, and doing mental calculations are difficult or impossible to master. According to GlynisHannell, author of *Dyscalculia: Action Plans for Successful Math Learning*, people with dyscalculia find mathematics to be tedious, irritating, and difficult to learn. "Their brains require more instruction, more concentrated learning experiences, and more practice to create these networks," (Haberstroh& Schulte-Körne, 2019).

Swars et al. (2006) observed the following characteristics of kids who struggle with mathematics learning, regardless of ambition, past instruction, or prior mathematical knowledge when they initially joined school:

- Show sluggish or incorrect recall of fundamental mathematical concepts;
- Respond to difficulties spontaneously and without inhibition;
- Have difficulties cognitively representing mathematical ideas;
- Have a weak grasp of numbers; and
- They have trouble maintaining knowledge in their working memory.

A long history of research in cognitive psychology has focused on the problems of forming numerical representations and learning how to utilize numbers in a variety of circumstances in mathematics (Clewell et al., 2005). There are no clear standards for identifying the existence or absence of LDs (learning problems), and there is still debate on a definition, operational criteria, and the prevalence of learning challenges in arithmetic. The phrase "Mathematical Learning Difficulty" (MLD) refers to a variety of challenges in arithmetic and problem solving in mathematics. There are many forms of mathematic learning challenges, which we'll refer to as "MLDs" in this section.

Classifications of MLD and the Hypothesis of Domain General Cognitive Deficit

According to the introduction, acquiring critical mathematical skills needs the presence as well as the growth and extension of a wide range of abilities. While it is true that understanding the structure of how numerical cognition develops is significantly reliant on basic number systems, they are not the only ones. Several studies have created MLD subgroups in a variety of methods. He made an important contribution by being among the first to link "Mathematics Disorder" to cognitive deficiencies. Gary and Hoard (2005) presented the following three primary kinds of deficiencies:

- Children with procedural (left hemisphere) learning difficulties have a delay in learning fundamental arithmetic operations. This might be related to issues with verbal working memory, but it could also be due to conceptual comprehension deficiencies.
- Children may suffer from semantic memory (left hemisphere) problems as a consequence of long-term memory loss, resulting in difficulties recalling information.
- Spatial impairments are defined as defects in the spatial representation of numbers (right hemisphere) in children.

As a result of Geary's categorization and other classifications presented in the literature, the three categories stated above, as well as one based on a loss of number knowledge, have been recognized as being relevant. Unfortunately, such classifications are unsatisfactory since the profiles of children seen in practice do

not seem to be linked with a single subtype, but rather are composed of multiple qualities associated with different subtypes in general, rather than with a single subtype (Desoete, 2007).

Classification Model of Mathematical Learning Difficulties

According to the literature as well as previously unreported clinical discoveries, there are four important cognitive areas where specific anomalies may be seen in MLD. These are as follows: Each subtype is also examined in terms of the systems that are involved as well as the usual mathematical issues that are encountered by students (Dean & Whiting, 2019).

Using an analysis of the distinct systems and problems suggested in each incorrect (or correct) answer to a set of well-designed tasks, it is feasible to uncover various areas of difficulty (and strength) in a student's performance on the exercises. Following this, a summary of the student's profile will be provided, which will highlight particular mathematical activities as well as any inadequacies in different systems (Shakespeare, 2017).

Who Conducts Learning Tests

Professionals in fields like as education, speech and language, audiology, and psychology are routinely called upon to assess children for learning difficulties. They conduct a battery of diagnostics, assessments, and interview questions in an attempt to determine what is interfering with your child's academic achievement and how to remedy the situation (Shakespeare, 2017).

When these tests are carried out, the findings may indicate a multitude of impairments ranging from difficulty in attention, language usage, or reading ability to hearing loss or impaired eyesight. There is now a tool or a solution available for almost every kind of learning impairment thanks to advances in technology; nevertheless, until the problem is properly identified, it is unlikely that anyone will be able to do anything to help (Gong et al., 2020).

Tests Used to Evaluate Learning

In order to determine whether a student has a learning disability in public schools, a series of tests must be administered. Many other tests may be done to determine whether a kid has a learning disability or not, such as IQ tests, achievement examinations and visual-motor integration tests. The evaluator's tastes and the needs of the child may need further tests (Dean & Whiting, 2019).

Types of Tests Used to Diagnose Learning Disabilities

Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) states that there cannot be a single test that may be used to determine a learning impairment (Shakespeare, 2017).

Intelligence Tests

Among the most often used IQ tests for detecting learning problems are the Wechsler Preschool and Primary Scales of Intelligence (commonly referred to as "IQ tests"), which measure pre-school and primary intelligence (Gong et al., 2020).

Achievement Tests

Achievement tests that are commonly used to determine whether or not a person has a learning disability include the Woodcock-Johnson Tests of Accomplishment (WJ), the Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT), the Wide Range Achievement Test (WRAT), and the Kaufman Test of Educational Achievement (KTEA) (Shakespeare, 2017).

Language Tests

Language evaluations including the Clinical Evaluation of Language Fundamentals (CELF), the Goldman Fristoe Test of Articulation, and the Test of Language Development are often used in the process of diagnosing difficulties related to learning (Dean & Whiting, 2019).

Analyzing Mathematics Performance

To complete any arithmetic assignment properly, students must: • think about the concepts in particular ways; visualize and speak them, model them, link them to what is previously learned, and challenge them; think about the ideas in specific ways. These are the methods for doing the duties. Manage the math activity; students must design a method for manipulating the data and choose the knowledge components that will be utilized (Dean & Whiting, 2019),

- Determine if paraphrasing, visualizing, or depicting concretely is suitable.
- When is it okay to take a pause and regroup?
- Check to check whether they are on the proper track, and if not, remedial action should be taken. In order to complete any work, they use the following strategies in the following order:
- Reading the data that describes the work is part of informing oneself about the job.
- They must be able to recognize the importance of each feature.
- Integrate or blend the meanings in the appropriate way.
- Make a difference between relevant and irrelevant data.
- Make a selection on how you want the end product to appear.
- They correlate the task with task categories they have already learned; they label it as an instance of a kind they have previously studied.

- Recognize and apply appropriate methods to the presented information, • recall particular numerical facts,
- They should maintain track of their progress and alter their techniques as needed to assess whether or not they were effective.

Research Methodology

The population is the total number of elements from which subjects are selected (Lakhan et al., 2020; Ali et al., 2021; Sajjad et al., 2022; Siddique et al., 2021). The participants in this descriptive research were eighth-grade students from public schools, who served as the study's population. The sample were the number of subjects chosen from the population (Siddique et al., 2020; Ali et al., 2021; Siddique et al., 2021). For the purposes of this research, a sample of 2392 eighth-grade students from public schools was selected at random for participation. In this study, the descriptive research approach was used to gather information.

Data Collection: Because of the absence of a screening checklist that fulfills local requirements for diagnosing learning impairments in the area of mathematics at the primary level in Punjab, this is the case in this province. The researcher developed a screening checklist that was used to collect information from children who were experiencing difficulties in arithmetic. Items were on the screening checklist were related to learning obstacles in the subject of mathematics. The screening checklist was administered by the researcher himself to instructors of mathematics in mainstream public schools in the Pakistani province of Punjab who were teaching pupils in the eighth grade in mathematics. This screening checklist for children with learning issues in mathematics was sent to the respondents and they had one week to complete it. The rules for responding to the screening checklist questions were sent to the responders in a timely manner.

Validity

Content Validity: Expert views were sought to determine the content validity of the exam. A panel of relevant field specialists was contacted. All of the experts have extensive experience teaching at the secondary school level in various institutions. They were knowledgeable in test design and development. The content components of the diagnostic exam were finalized for future investigation based on the experts' recommendations.

Concurrent Validity

Table

Concurrent validity of Learning Difficulties Diagnostic Test of Mathematics

Scale Factor	Correlation with Achievement Test
Pre –Number Diagnostic Test	.83
Number Diagnostic Test	.79
Arithmetic Operation Diagnostic Test	.89
Geometry Diagnostic Test	.81

Data Analysis & Interpretation:

The data was scored and entered into the SPSS computer software once it was collected. In this study, descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data. For the purposes of determining the reliability of the screening checklist, Cronbach's Alpha was utilized, and the Pearson correlation coefficient was used to evaluate the concurrent validity of the screening checklist. For the purpose of comparing the performance of low and high scores, an independent sample t-test was conducted. The information gathered during the research is shown in the tables below.

Table

Pearson's' Correlation Coefficient for the LDMDT for Concurrent Validity

Test	Correlation with Achievement Test
Learning Difficulties Mathematics Diagnostic Test	.80**
Pre –Number Diagnostic Test	.63**
Number Diagnostic Test	.76**
Arithmetic Operation Diagnostic Test	.60**
Geometry Diagnostic Test	.79**

**P < .05 Level of significance

Table

Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for the Identification of Reliability of the Screening Checklist

Scale Factor	No. of Items	Coefficients
Screening Checklist for Students with Learning Difficulties (SCLDM)	30	.83
Learning Difficulties Mathematics Diagnostic Test (LDMDT)	53	.80
Pre –Number Diagnostic Test	8	.85
Number Diagnostic Test	10	.79
Arithmetic Operation Diagnostic Test	23	.82
Geometry Diagnostic Test	12	.90

Table

Item Difficulty Level of Pre-Number Diagnostic Test

Sr#	Item	Difficulty Level
1	PNDT- ₁	.69
2	PNDT- ₂	.53
3	PNDT- ₃	.44
4	PNDT- ₄	.65
5	PNDT- ₅	.45
6	PNDT- ₆	.56
7	PNDT- ₇	.77
8	PNDT- ₈	.61

Table

Item Difficulty Level of Number Diagnostic Test

Sr#	Item	Difficulty Level
1	NDT- ₁	.69
2	NDT- ₂	.53
3	NDT- ₃	.44
4	NDT- ₄	.65
5	NDT- ₅	.45
6	NDT- ₆	.56
7	NDT- ₇	.77
8	NDT- ₈	.61
9	NDT- ₉	.47
10	NDT- ₁₀	.45

Table

Item Difficulty Level of Arithmetic Operation Diagnostic Test (AODT)

Sr#	Item	Difficulty Index	Sr#	Item	Difficulty Index
1	AODT-1	.43	13	AODT-13	.53
2	AODT-2	.33	14	AODT-14	.39
3	AODT-3	.37	15	AODT-15	.41
4	AODT-4	.37	16	AODT-16	.55
5	AODT-5	.50	17	AODT-17	.29
6	AODT-6	.34	18	AODT-18	.31
7	AODT-7	.32	19	AODT-19	.25
8	AODT-8	.46	20	AODT-20	.67
9	AODT-9	.41	21	AODT-21	.35
10	AODT-10	.35	22	AODT-22	.41
11	AODT-11	.36	23	AODT-23	.33
12	AODT-12	.49			

Table
Item Difficulty level of Geometry Diagnostic Test (GDT)

Sr#	Item	Difficulty Index	Sr#	Item	Difficulty Index
1	GDT-1	.74	7	GDT-7	.31
2	GDT-2	.57	8	GDT-8	.60
3	GDT-3	.49	9	GDT-9	.35
4	GDT-4	.54	10	GDT-10	.39
5	GDT-5	.53	11	GDT-11	.39
6	GDT-6	.42	12	GDT-12	.43

Table
Item Discrimination Index of Pre-Number Diagnostic Test (PNDT)

Sr#	Item	Discrimination Index
1	PNDT-1	.23
2	PNDT-2	.32
3	PNDT-3	.31
4	PNDT-4	.71
5	PNDT-5	.50
6	PNDT-6	.48
7	PNDT-7	.69
8	PNDT-8	.67

Table
Item Discrimination Index of Number Diagnostic Test (NDT)

Sr#	Item	Difficulty Index	Sr#	Item	Difficulty Index
1	NDT-1	.71	6	NDT-6	.31
2	NDT-2	.25	7	NDT-7	.38
3	NDT-3	.03	8	NDT-8	.61
4	NDT-4	.27	9	NDT-9	.74
5	NDT-5	-.10	10	NDT-10	.80

Table
Item Discrimination Index Arithmetic Operation Diagnostic Test (AODT)

Sr#	Item	Difficulty Index	Sr#	Item	Difficulty Index
1	AODT-1	.51	13	AODT-12	.67
2	AODT-2	.51	14	AODT-13	.39
3	AODT-3	.31	15	AODT-14	.48
4	AODT-4	.41	16	AODT-15	.26
5	AODT-5	.80	17	AODT-16	.60
6	AODT-6	.52	18	AODT-17	.33
7	AODT-7	.16	19	AODT-18	.25
8	AODT-8	.27	20	AODT-19	.32
9	AODT-9	.25	21	AODT-20	.38
10	AODT-10	.33	22	AODT-21	.37
11	AODT-11	.29	23	AODT-22	.61
12	AODT-12	.30			

Table
Item Discrimination Index of Geometry Diagnostic Test (GDT)

Sr#	Item	Difficulty Index	Sr#	Item	Difficulty Index
1	GDT-1	.40	7	GDT-7	.52
2	GDT-2	.70	8	GDT-8	.66
3	GDT-3	.25	9	GDT-9	.38
4	GDT-4	.28	10	GDT-10	.39
5	GDT-5	.36	11	GDT-11	.46
6	GDT-6	.62	12	GDT-12	.80

*P < .05 Level of Significance

Table
Achievement Comparison for Pre-Number

Achievement Level	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Low Achiever	424	.82	2390	-20.625	.001
High Achiever	1968	4.37	270.041		

**P* < .05 Level of Significance

Table illustrates that there is a substantial difference in the opinion of respondents at the base of their achievement regarding subject math.

Table
Achievement Comparison for Number Concept

Achievement Level	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Low Achiever	384	.51	2390	-24.635	.000
High Achiever	2008	3.93	2271.0		

**P* < .05 Level of Significance

Table displays that there is a substantial difference in the opinion of respondents at the base of their achievement regarding subject math.

Table
Achievement Comparison for Arithmetic Operations

Achievement Level	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Low Achiever	272	.48	2390	-11.628	.000
High Achiever	2120	7.54	2361		

**P* < .05 Level of Significance

Table displays that there is a significant variance in the opinion of respondents at the base of their achievement regarding subject math.

Table
Achievement Comparison for Geometry

Achievement Level	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Low Achiever	356	0.38	2390	-21.372	.000
High Achiever	2036	5.02	2257.00		

**P* < .05 Level of Significance

Table shows that there is a significant difference in the opinion of respondents at the base of their achievement regarding subject math.

Table
Achievement Comparison for Subject Math

Achievement Level	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Low Achiever	371	21.5116	1224	-2.517	.001
High Achiever	2021	33.6196	1163		

**P* < .05 Level of Significance

Table shows that there is a significant difference in the opinion of respondents at the base of their achievement regarding subject math.

Screening Checklist Scores Frequencies

Table
Frequency Distribution of Responses of Teachers of Screening Checklist Learning Difficulties in Mathematics

Score Range	Frequency	Percentage (%)
30-33	1663	53
34-37	779	25
38-41	269	9
42-45	210	7
46-48	199	6
Total	3120	100

Learning Difficulties in Mathematics Diagnostic Test (LDMDT)

Second, we'll look at how many male and female students live in different parts of the country and how often those kids struggle with arithmetic learning. Researchers used independent sample t-tests to discover gender differences in students' learning challenges, as well as differences in students' geographic areas and academic levels of achievement.

Item Wise Frequency Distribution of Students

Table
Frequency Distribution of Item Wise Responses of the Students in Pre-Number Diagnostic Test (PNDT)

Sr. No	Item	Correct		Wrong		Not Responded		Total	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1	P. 1	1774 (74.2)		578 (24.1)		40 (1.7)		2392 (100)	
2	Sr. No ² 2	1616 (67.6)		748 (31.1)		28 (1.2)		2392 (100)	
3	P. 3	1316 (55.0)		1044 (43.6)		32 (1.3)		2392 (100)	
4	1 P. 4	N. 1 1236 (51.7)		1028 (42.97)		128 (5.4)		2392 (100)	
4	2 P. 4	N. 2 1434 (59.9)		934 (39)		24 (1)		2392 (100)	
5	3 P. 5	N. 3 684 (28.6)		1556 (65.05)		152 (6.4)		2392 (100)	
5	4 P. 5	N. 4 1426 (59.6)		910 (38)		56 (2.3)		2392 (100)	
6	5 P. 6	N. 5 240 (10)		2028 (84.78)		124 (5.2)		2392 (100)	
6	6 P. 6	N. 6 868 (36.3)		1432 (59.87)		92 (3.8)		2392 (100)	
7	7 P. 7	N. 7 1398 (58.4)		894 (37.37)		100 (4.2)		2392 (100)	
7	8 P. 7	N. 8 1302 (54.4)		978 (40.8)		112 (4.7)		2392 (100)	
8	9 P. 8	N. 9 900 (37.6)		1324 (55.35)		168 (7)		2392 (100)	
8	10 P. 8	N. 10 1146 (47)		1202 (50.27)		44 (1.8)		2392 (100)	
				504 (21.1)		176 (7.4)		2392 (100)	
				912 (38.1)		1248 (52.17)		232 (9.7)	
				898 (37.4)		1310 (54.76)		188 (7.9)	
				1172 (49)		1068 (44.64)		152 (6.4)	
				1160 (48.5)		1022 (42.72)		210 (8.8)	

Table
Frequency Distribution of Item Wise Responses of the Students in Pre-Number Diagnostic Test (NDT)

Table

Frequency Distribution of Item Wise Responses of the Students in Arithmetic Operations Diagnostic Test (AODT)

Sr. No	Item	Correct		Wrong		Not Responded		Total	
		<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
1	A ₁	896	(37.5)	1456	(60.86)	40	(1.7)	2392	(100)
2	A ₂	698	(29.2)	1598	(66.80)	96	(4)	2392	(100)
3	A ₃	428	(17.9)	1896	(79.26)	68	(2.8)	2392	(100)
4	A ₄	706	(29.5)	1478	(61.78)	208	(8.7)	2392	(100)
5	A ₅	1374	(57.4)	918	(38.37)	100	(4.2)	2392	(100)
6	A ₆	1054	(44.1)	1134	(47.40)	204	(8.5)	2392	(100)
7	A ₇	360	(15.1)	1664	(69.56)	368	(15.4)	2392	(100)
8	A ₈	408	(17.1)	1752	(73.24)	232	(9.7)	2392	(100)
9	A ₉	1098	(45.9)	1110	(46.40)	184	(7.7)	2392	(100)
10	A ₁₀	702	(29.3)	1514	(63.29)	176	(7.4)	2392	(100)
11	A ₁₁	372	(15.6)	1816	(75.91)	204	(8.5)	2392	(100)
12	A ₁₂	466	(19.5)	1542	(64.46)	384	(16.1)	2392	(100)
13	A ₁₃	1096	(45.8)	1048	(43.81)	248	(10.4)	2392	(100)
14	A ₁₄	766	(32)	1410	(58.94)	216	(9)	2392	(100)
15	A ₁₅	1020	(42.6)	1150	(48)	222	(9.3)	2392	(100)
16	A ₁₆	1294	(54.1)	852	(35.62)	246	(10.3)	2392	(100)
17	A ₁₇	1048	(43.8)	1134	(47.40)	210	(8.8)	2392	(100)
18	A ₁₈	808	(33.8)	1322	(55.26)	262	(11)	2392	(100)
19	A ₁₉	480	(20.1)	1586	(66.30)	326	(13.6)	2392	(100)
20	A ₂₀	652	(27.3)	1530	(63.96)	210	(8.8)	2392	(100)
21	A ₂₁	524	(21.9)	1414	(59.11)	454	(19)	2392	(100)
22	A ₂₂	792	(33.1)	1226	(51.25)	454	(19)	2392	(100)
23	A ₂₃	748	(31.3)	1390	(58.15)	254	(10.6)	2392	(100)

Table
Frequency Distribution of Item Wise Responses of the Students in Geometry Diagnostic Test (GDT)

Sr. No	Item	Correct		Wrong		Not Responded		Total	
		<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
1	G ₁	1814	(75.8)	436	(18.22)	142	(5.9)	2392	(100)
2	G ₂	1480	(61.9)	782	(32.69)	130	(5.4)	2392	(100)

3	G. 3	1124 (47)	1050 (43.89)	218 (9.1)	2392 (100)
4	G. 4	1174 (49.1)	988 (41.30)	230 (9.6)	2392 (100)
5	G. 5	522 (21.8)	1616 (67.55)	254 (10.6)	2392 (100)
6	G. 6	904 (37.8)	1278 (53.4)	210 (8.8)	2392 (100)
7	G. 7	848 (35.)	1330 (55.6)	214 (8.9)	2392 (100)
8	G. 8	972 (40.6)	1046 (43.72)	374 (15.6)	2392 (100)
9	G. 9	824 (34.4)	1162 (48.57)	406 (17)	2392 (100)
10	G. 10	444 (18.6)	1602 (66.97)	346 (14.5)	2392 (100)
11	G. 11	756 (31.6)	1266 (52.92)	370 (15.5)	2392 (100)
12	G. 12	1040(43.5)	970 (40.55)	382(16)	2392 (100)

Prevalence of Students with Learning Difficulties in Mathematics Using Discrepancy Formula

Table

Prevalence of Students with Learning Difficulties in Pre-Number Concepts

Conceptual Areas /Mathematical skills	Total No. of students assessed	No. of students with learning difficulties	Prevalence of students with learning difficulties
Pre-Number Concepts	2392	424	$\frac{424}{2392} \times 100\% = 17.7\%$

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table

Prevalence of Students with Learning Difficulties in Number Concepts

Conceptual Areas /Mathematical skills	Total No. of students assessed	No. of students with learning difficulties	Prevalence of students with learning difficulties
Number Concepts	2392	384	$\frac{384}{2392} \times 100\% = 16\%$

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table

Prevalence of Students with Learning Difficulties in Arithmetic Operation of Number Concepts

Conceptual Areas /Mathematical skills	Total No. of students assessed	No. of students with learning difficulties	Prevalence of students with learning difficulties
Arithmetic Operations (+, -, ×, ÷)	2392	272	$\frac{272}{2392} \times 100\% = 11.4\%$

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table

Prevalence of Students with Learning Difficulties in Geometry Related Concepts

Conceptual Areas /Mathematical skills	Total No. of students assessed	No. of students with learning difficulties	Prevalence of students with learning difficulties
Geometry	2392	356	$\frac{356}{2392} \times 100\% = 14.9\%$

P* < .05 Level of SignificanceTable***Overall Prevalence of Male Students with Learning Difficulties in Mathematics*

Conceptual Areas /Mathematical skills	Total No. of students assessed	No. of students with learning difficulties	Prevalence of students with learning difficulties
Learning Difficulties Mathematics Diagnostic Test /LDMDT	2392	371	$\frac{371}{2392} \times 100\% = 15.6\%$

P* < .05 Level of SignificancePrevalence of Female Students with Learning Difficulties in the Subject of Mathematics at Primary Level****Table***Prevalence of Female Students with Learning Difficulties in Pre-Number Concepts*

Conceptual Areas /Mathematical skills	Total No. of students assessed	No. of students with learning difficulties	Prevalence of students with learning difficulties
Pre-Number Concepts	2392	319	$\frac{319}{2392} \times 100\% = 27.5\%$

P* < .05 Level of SignificanceTable***Prevalence of Female Students with Learning Difficulties in Number Concepts*

Conceptual Areas /Mathematical skills	Total No. of students assessed	No. of students with learning difficulties	Prevalence of students with learning difficulties
Number Concepts	2392	223	$\frac{223}{2392} \times 100\% = 19.2\%$

P* < .05 Level of SignificanceTable***Prevalence of Female Students with Learning Difficulties in Arithmetic Operation of Number Concepts*

Conceptual Areas /Mathematical skills	Total No. of students assessed	No. of students with learning difficulties	Prevalence of students with learning difficulties
Arithmetic Operations (+, -, x, ÷)	2392	192	$\frac{30}{2392} \times 100\% = 16.5\%$

P* < .05 Level of SignificanceTable***Prevalence of Female Students with Learning Difficulties in Geometry Related Concepts*

Conceptual Areas /Mathematical skills	Total No. of students assessed	No. of students with learning difficulties	Prevalence of students with learning difficulties
Geometry	2392	206	$\frac{206}{2392} \times 100\% = 17.7\%$

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table

Overall Prevalence of Female Students with Learning Difficulties in Mathematics

Conceptual Areas /Mathematical skills	Total No. of students assessed	No. of students with learning difficulties	Prevalence of students with learning difficulties
Learning Difficulties Mathematics Diagnostic Test /LDMDT	2392	483	$\frac{206}{2392} \times 100\% = 20.2\%$

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Prevalence of Male Students with Learning Difficulties in the Subject of Mathematics at Primary Level

Table

Prevalence of Male Students with Learning Difficulties in Pre-Number Concepts

Conceptual Areas /Mathematical skills	Total No. of students assessed	No. of students with learning difficulties	Prevalence of students with learning difficulties
Pre-Number Concepts	2392	287	$\frac{287}{2392} \times 100\% = 23.2\%$

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table

Prevalence of Male Students with Learning Difficulties in Number Concepts

Conceptual Areas /Mathematical skills	Total No. of students assessed	No. of students with learning difficulties	Prevalence of students with learning difficulties
Number Concepts	2392	180	$\frac{180}{2392} \times 100\% = 14.6\%$

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table

Prevalence of Male Students with Learning Difficulties in Arithmetic Operation of Number Concepts

Conceptual Areas /Mathematical skills	Total No. of students assessed	No. of students with learning difficulties	Prevalence of students with learning difficulties
Arithmetic Operations (+, -, ×, ÷)	2392	129	$\frac{129}{2392} \times 100\% = 10.5\%$

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table*Prevalence of Male Students with Learning Difficulties in Geometry Related Concepts*

Conceptual Areas /Mathematical skills	Total No. of students assessed	No. of students with learning difficulties	Prevalence of students with learning difficulties
Geometry	2392	165	$\frac{165}{2392} \times 100\% = 13.4\%$

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table*Overall Prevalence of Male Students with Learning Difficulties in Mathematics*

Conceptual Areas /Mathematical skills	Total No. of students assessed	No. of students with learning difficulties	Prevalence of students with learning difficulties
Learning Difficulties Mathematics Diagnostic Test /LDMDT	2392	368	$\frac{368}{2392} \times 100\% = 15.4\%$

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Gender Difference in Prevalence of Learning Difficulties in Mathematics**Table***Comparison of Opinion of Respondents for Learning Difficulties in Pre-Number*

Groups	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Male	1161	6.03	2114	-3.938	.060
Female	1231	6.54	4172.466		

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table describes that there is no significant difference in the opinion of respondents at the base of their gender.

Table*Comparison of Opinion of Respondents for Learning Difficulties in Number Concept*

Groups	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Male	1161	7.96	1904	.7.725	.000
Female	1231	6.16	1268.437		

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table describes that there is a significant difference in the opinion of respondents at the base of their gender.

Table*Comparison of Opinion of Respondents for Learning Difficulties in Arithmetic Operations*

Groups	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Male	1161	16.05	1460	1.909	.042
Female	1231	15.33	1216		

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table describes that there is no significant difference in the opinion of respondents at the base of their gender.

Table

Comparison of Opinion of Respondents for Learning Difficulties in Geometry

Groups	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Male	1161	8.92	1904	.464	.000
Female	1231	7.74	1268		

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table describes that there is a significant difference in the opinion of respondents at the base of their gender.

Table

Comparison of Opinion of Respondents for Learning Difficulties in Mathematics

Groups	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Male	1161	31.262	1224	4.908	.008
Female	1231	29.3518	993.18		

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table describes that there is a significant difference in the opinion of respondents at the base of their gender.

Difference in Prevalence of Students with Learning Difficulties in LDMDT among Students with respect to Residential Area at Primary Level

Table

Comparison of Opinion of Respondents for Learning Difficulties in Pre-Numbers

Living Area	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Rural	1243	6.69	2086	-1.401	.005
Urban	1149	7.01	2114		

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table describes that there is a significant difference in the opinion of respondents at the base of their living area.

Table

Comparison of Opinion of Respondents for Learning Difficulties in Numbers

Living Area	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Rural	1243	7.01	1372	-1.127	.006
Urban	1149	7.75	1460		

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table describes that there is a significant difference in the opinion of respondents at the base of their living area.

Table

Comparison of Opinion of Respondents for Learning Difficulties in Arithmetic Operation

Living Area	N	M	df	t	Sig
Rural	1243	16.41	1851	-1.497	.009
Urban	1149	18.21	1851		

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table describes that there is a significant difference in the opinion of respondents at the base of their living area.

Table

Comparison of Opinion of Respondents for Learning Difficulties in Geometry

Living Area	N	Mean	Df	t	Sig
Rural	1243	7.99	1882	-2.623	.059
Urban	1149	8.42	1904		

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table describes that there is no significant difference in the opinion of respondents at the base of their living area.

Table

Comparison of Opinion of Respondents for Learning Difficulties in Subject Mathematics

Living Area	N	M	df	t	Sig
Rural	1243	31.51	1224	-2.517	.002
Urban	1149	33.61	1163		

**P < .05 Level of Significance*

Table describes that there is a significant difference in the opinion of respondents at the base of their living area.

Findings

It was decided to convene a panel of experts in the relevant area to offer their opinions in order to evaluate the content validity of the screening checklist for children with learning challenges in mathematics, which was developed. It was determined that the Cronbach's alpha statistic, in conjunction with data analysis, was reliable when used to determine the dependability of a screening checklist for children with learning difficulties in mathematics. It was shown via the use of the Pearson correlation coefficient that the screening checklist for children with learning difficulties in mathematics was valid when used in conjunction with other screening tools. According to the results of the research, the screening checklist had a Cronbach's alpha of .93 and a Pearson correlation value of .89, indicating that it was reliable. Statistically significant differences were found between the children who had low scores on the screening checklist and those who received high scores on the same checklist.

Conclusion and discussion

It was the goal of this research to develop and validate the diagnostic test for the mathematics for the students in mathematics at the primary level in Punjab. The participants in this study were students with learning challenges in mathematics at the basic level in Punjab. The integrity of the screening checklist, both in terms of its appearance and its substance, was confirmed by industry specialists. The Cronbach's alpha test was used to

determine the reliability of the screening checklist, and the results were positive. The screening checklist, in addition, is capable of discriminating between pupils who are poor achievers and those who are high achievers.

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- Yogesh Hole et al 2019 J. Phys.: Conf. Ser. 1362 012121

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